

CRISIS ON THE INDIAN ECONOMIC FORUM WHILST COVID – ANALYSIS OF ALL SECTORS OF THE INDUSTRY ON BASIS OF POLICY FORMULATION

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Research Objectives

- To examine the economic reforms brought in during covid times.
- Critical analysis of the paradigm shift in contribution of each sector in the economy of the country.
- Contribution and growth of the Multi-functional banking system with Ease of doing business in the country.

Research Questions

- Why did the Lower section of the economy collapsed significantly?
- Which segment of the Industry suffered the most losses?
- Which segments benefitted from the same?
- How did the Banking system aid in the economic recovery ?

Statement of Problem

The Indian economy stands 6th in the entire world and in terms of growth rate it stands at the second fastest growing economy, which faced a major set back in the year 2020 due to the advent of the novel Corona Virus. The virus did not only caused loss of life but also major economic losses. Almost all the sectors of the economy had faced huge losses due to the virus spread and continuous lock down. Indian economy had seen a dip of 7.3% from a growth rate of 6% p.a. The Index of the

Industrial Production provides data on organized manufacturing, that is small scale factories. It specifies that the crisis has hit the smaller industries in the unorganized sector which employs around 80% workforce of the country. Industries like tourism, automobile, real estate etc. got affected to a considerable extent. A 50 percent decline in overall revenue was seen in the tourism sector, which contributes about 6.23 percent of the nation's GDP. To boost domestic manufacturing, increase exports, and make the nation an essential component of the global supply chain, the government launched the production-linked incentive (PLI) scheme for 10 industries, covering a wide range of products and technologies.

The government also increased FDI in defence manufacturing under the automatic route from 49 per cent to 74 per cent with the aim of promoting indigenisation of defence production under its Make-in-India initiative. After the economic stoppage, the International Labor Organization has projected that **400 million people in India risk falling into poverty**. Industries like software and e-learning, pharmaceuticals as well as textile industries got a boost during the covid crisis when the other sectors were on the verge of shutting down.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis will be a situation where the post covid scenario becomes the new normal along with the variations in the economic policies of the country.

Research Methodology

The research methodology used in the doctrine source journal is secondary. The content for the research journal has been derived from various articles, newsletters and papers. Also the zest of it has been extracted from government websites .

History of Industrialization in India

During the colonial period, India followed a non-industrial model as a developing country. However, a significant number of Indians saw this model as a barrier to growth, believing that only industrialization could maximise the country's economic growth. Following independence, India's first Prime Minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, used industrialization to eradicate poverty in the country. With the introduction of industrialization, there was a significant amount of growth through the flow of internal and external economies that pushed the country towards self-sufficiency. Furthermore, the government recognised that the potential of exports and agriculture was limited, so taxation was imposed based on the terms of trade. The country's heavy industry was given attention by emphasising import substitution. Only the implementation of a centralized and planned economy could catalyse the introduction of industrialization in India. Administrative control began with the passage of **The Industries Act of 1951**, which focused on industry development and regulation. While many East Asian countries were focusing on building strong private sectors through state intervention, India was focusing on state regulation of key industries during the same time period. Rural electrification and state activism in subsidising new seeds and fertilisers were two major shifts in Indian industrialization in the mid-19th century.

Nehru believed that a strong state with a centralised planned economy was required for the country to rapidly industrialise. The **Industries (Development and Regulation) Act (IDRA) of 1951** laid the groundwork for this administrative control over industrial capacity. However, as time passed,

the licencing requirements became increasingly stringent, accompanied by a slew of procedures requiring approval from a number of disparate and uncoordinated ministries¹.

Two major shifts in the role of the state occurred during Prime Minister Indhira Gandhi's (1966-77) tenure. First, the neglect of agriculture was reversed through state activism in the form of subsidies for new seeds and fertilizers, agricultural credit, and rural electrification. The green revolution took off, and by the mid-1970s, India was self-sufficient in grain. The second shift was a tightening of state control over all aspects of the economy. Banks were nationalised, trade was increasingly restricted, price controls were imposed on a wide range of products, and foreign investment was restricted.

The **Foreign Exchange and Regulation Act** came into effect in 1973, regulating both foreign exchange transactions and foreign investment (FERA). In the 1970s and 1980s, the act effectively blocked the inflow of new technology from abroad, particularly when large equity stakes were involved.

Economic Sectors of India

Economic activities result in the production of goods and services, whereas sectors are groups of economic activities classified according to certain criteria. The Indian economy can be divided into sectors based on ownership, working conditions, and the nature of the activities. During the early stages of civilization, all economic activity was in the primary sector. Following the surplus production of food, people's demand for other products increased, resulting in the development of the secondary sector. During the nineteenth century's industrial revolution, the growth of the secondary sector spread its influence. A support system was required to facilitate industrial activity. Certain industries, such as transportation and finance, were critical in sustaining industrial activity.

Development of MSME or SSI in India

¹ Jana Hambrock and Sebastian Hauptmann, *Industrialisation in India*, https://www.tcd.ie/Economics/assets/pdf/SER/1999/Hambrock_Hauptman.pdf

Over the last seven decades, the MSME has emerged as a highly vibrant and dynamic sector of the Indian economy. It is critical in providing employment at a lower capital cost and in reducing regional imbalances by industrializing rural and backward areas. It is also a complementary and ancillary unit for large industry, and it makes significant contributions to the country's socioeconomic development. Prior to the passage of the **Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Development (MSMED) Act in 2006**, the non-agriculture MSME segment in India was heterogeneous, consisting primarily of traditional industries such as coir, khadi, and silk, **Small Scale Service and Business Enterprises (SSSBEs), Small Scale Industries (SSIs)**, Cottage and Village Industries. All of this is commonly referred to as Small Scale Industries (SSI).

The MSME Act of 2006 incorporated all diverse industries, as well as the service sector and medium enterprises. At the moment, the MSME sector in India is broadly divided into two categories: manufacturing and service industry. It is further classified as micro, small, or enterprise based on their investments in plant and machinery or equipment. In the Indian economy, the MSME has emerged as a prominent sector that contributes significantly to exports, job creation, and entrepreneurship development, as well as the socioeconomic development of rural and backward areas at a lower capital cost than large enterprises. According to Ministry of MSME estimates, it accounts for approximately 40% of total industrial production, as well as 45 percent of total manufacturing output and 40% of total exports of the country².

Contribution of MSME sector in Nation Building

The MSMEs sector's contribution to the country's gross value added (GVA) has been steadily expanding. Over time, the proportion of MSMEs in total GVA and total GDP has risen. In the country, there are 633.88 lakh MSMEs engaged in various economic activities. Manufacturing operations account for 31% of MSMEs, while trade accounts for 36%, and other services account for 33%. The micro-sector enterprises account for more than 99 percent of total estimated numbers within the defined sectors, while the small and medium sectors account for only 0.52 percent and 0.01 percent of total estimated MSMEs, respectively. Another point to consider is that of the total

² A Sathish and S. Rajamohan, MSME IN INDIA – WHAT WENT BEFORE?, ZIJBM VOL 8 ISSUE 9, Page 2-3, (2018).

estimated MSMEs, 51 percent are in rural India and 49 percent are in urban areas. The ownership distribution of MSMEs in different areas can be presented as follows:

- Male dominance in enterprise ownership is visible in all areas, with 79.63 percent of enterprises owned by men compared to 20.37 percent owned by women. Female ownership is more concentrated in rural areas, particularly in microenterprises, than in urban areas³.
- Socially disadvantaged groups own 66.27 percent of all MSMEs (SC, ST and OBC). Specifically in rural and urban areas, many MSMEs are owned by OBCs (49.72 percent). The same picture of category-wise distribution can be seen in different sectors of the industry. According to the NSS's 73rd round report, 1109.89 lakh employees of the MSMEs sector work in various activities such as 360.41 lakh in manufacturing, 387.18 lakh in trade, 362.22 lakh in other services, and 0.07 lakh in the country's non-captive electricity generation and transmission work.
- Only the micro-sector employs 1076.19 lakh people, accounting for approximately 97 percent of total employment, while the small and medium sectors employ 2.88 percent and 0.16 percent, respectively. Male employees account for 844.68 lakh (76 percent) of total employment, while female employees account for 264.92 lakh (24 percent).

Covid Impact on MSME sector

The MSMEs sector contributes significantly to the Indian economy's growth. Prior to the COVID-19 upheaval, this sector was experiencing sluggish growth due to a slew of challenges such as a lack of financial support, a lack of proper infrastructural facilities, a lack of advanced technology, and so on. However, the process of de-monetization (2016) and the Goods and Services Tax (GST) have exacerbated the problems (2017). **Because the majority of MSMEs rely on unskilled labor in rural areas, minor issues have a greater impact on these businesses**, and a health crisis like this jeopardizes their potential and sustainability.

COVID-19 has altered the operational environment for MSMEs. The most stringent lockdown to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 crisis resulted in the greatest shock for the MSMEs sector, particularly for the smallest firms. The sudden announcement to follow all protocols of COVID-

³ Ministry of MSMEs, Annual Report (2020–2021).

19 emergency in the process of production causes supply chain problems such as raw material import for cross-state and cross-country border, panic migration of labor force to their native places, procurement of perishable products, monetary crunch, etc., generate unemployment, consumer fear element, demand side problems, price rise, malfunctioning, reduced profit, and so on.

The MSMEs sector is in the worst possible shape, with a 55 percent loss in employment, production falling from an average of 75 percent capacity to just 11 percent, a 17.2 percent loss in annual sales, a delay in raw material receipt, less possibility of paying wages, more labor shortages, and lost access to credit. Overall, 70% of firms report that they will not survive the crisis beyond the next three months if the lockdown continues, and the smallest one may fail in one month⁴. According to a survey of 5,000 MSMEs conducted by the All India Manufacturers Organisation, The Hindu reported that 71% of firms are unable to pay their employees' salaries. At the moment, approximately 25% of firms in India will be forced to close if the lockdown extends beyond 4 weeks, while 43% will be forced to close if the lockdown extends beyond 8 weeks. Unfortunately, the lockdown period continues with some relaxation, which will worsen the situation beyond imagination⁵.

Government Response to support

The government has announced the Emergency Credit Line Guarantee Scheme, which is the biggest fiscal component of the ₹20 lakh crore Aatmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan package, in May. The main purpose of the package is to enhance businesses with a major focus on the MSMEs sector. The initiatives are as follows:

1. MSMEs have been redefined in terms of both investment limits and turnover size. Increased the investment limit for micro units in the manufacturing sector from 25 lakh to 5 crore and in the service sector from 10 lakh to 2 crore, which is now 1 crore, for small units in the manufacturing sector from 25 lakh to 5 crore and in the service sector from 10 lakh to 2 crore, which is now 10 crore, and for medium units in the manufacturing sector

⁴ Ghosh, 2020; Rathore, 2020; WTO, 2020

⁵ *The Hindu*, 2020

from 5 crore to 10 crore and in the service sector from 2 crore to 5 crore. Introduced additional criteria of turnover for micro, it is 5 crore, for small 50 crore, and for medium it is 100 crore for both manufacturing and services in investment and turnover⁶.

2. The RBI also took some initiatives, such as lowering the repo rate; as a result, the bank can lend at a lower rate, assisting the MSMEs sector. The State Bank of India has set a target of '700 crore for MSMEs in Mumbai.
3. The government announced a collateral-free automatic loan worth 3 lakh crore and did not repay for 12 months to support the struggling MSMEs sector. This will help 45 lakh MSMEs units across the country in restarting business activity and safeguarding jobs. For the strained MSMEs, the government will provide 20,000 crore subordinated debt. A fund is created for the MSMEs sector that will be injecting 50,000 crore equity.
4. To compete and supply in government tenders, global tenders will be banned for government procurement up to 200 crore, which will support '**Make in India**' and move the country closer to self-sufficiency. All commitments made by the government of India and central public sector enterprises (CPSEs) will be honoured. MSMEs must pay their invoices within 45 days⁷.
5. E-market linkage for MSMEs has begun as a replacement for trade fairs and exhibitions. Fintech will improve transaction-based lending for MSMEs that are currently facing marketing and liquidity issues as a result of the e-data. market's COVID-19.
6. The government has decided to provide PF and EPF support for both businesses and workers by providing a liquidity relief of '6,750 crore to reduce the financial stress of businesses. Employer and employee PF contributions have been reduced from 12% to 10% for all official establishments under EPFO in order to increase liquidity in the hands of consumers and producers, but CPSEs and state PSUs will continue to pay 12% as an employer contribution. Around 6.5 lakh employers and 4.3 crore employees will benefit from the government's assistance. This benefit is also available under the PM Garib Kalyan Package to workers who are not eligible for 24 percent EPF support⁸.

⁶ Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). (2006). The micro, small and medium enterprises development act, 2006. <https://msme.gov.in/sites/default/files/gazette%20596-E-English.pdf>

⁷ Ministry of MSMEs. (2018–2019). Annual report 2018–2019. Government of India. Ministry of MSMEs. (2020–2021). Annual report 2020–2021. Government of India.

⁸ Prasad, R., & Mondal, A. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Indian economy with special reference to Indian MSMEs sector. Research Gate, XV(7), 16–21

7. Furthermore, in order to increase taxpayer liquidity, the government announced a 25% reduction in the TDS rate for SMEs, NBFCs, and TCS. The government has decided that the income-tax return for fiscal year 2019–2020 will be extended from July 31, 2020 to July 31, 2021 as part of direct tax measures. From the 30th of October 2020 to the 30th of November 2020, and from the 30th of September 2020 to the 31st of October 2020, tax audits will be conducted. 2020. The government also announced that all pending refunds to charitable trusts and noncorporate businesses and professions, including sole proprietorships, partnerships, LLPs, and co-operatives, would be made. shall be issued immediately.

Contribution of Other Sectors of Indian Economy

Tertiary Sector

The tertiary industry is a technical term for the economy's services sector, which includes a diverse range of businesses such as financial institutions, schools, hotels, and restaurants. The tertiary industry is one of three primary industrial types in a developed economy, the other two being primary (i.e., raw materials) and secondary (i.e., goods production). As an economy develops, its focus shifts from primary to secondary and tertiary industries.

The service sector can be classified using either the country's own definition or the United Nations Central Product Classification (UNCPC). The UNCPC serves as a foundation for international negotiations such as those of the World Trade Organization (WTO). The National Industrial Classification in India categorises services. Both have changed as the industry has evolved. At the moment, the National Industrial Classification 2008 is used, though there are differences between it and the UNCPC, for example, construction is not a sector in India but is in the UNCPC. Many services lack disaggregated data. Government agencies such as the Central Statistical Organization and the National Sample Survey Organization, both under the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, as well as the Reserve Bank of India, have been involved attempting to collect and collate disaggregated data; however, because services such as retailing

and Construction is mostly done in the non-corporate (informal or unorganised) sector, but there is some formalisation misreporting and underreporting⁹.

Contribution in the Economy: The share of GDP accounted for by services has increased while agriculture's has decreased. In the last decade, the share of services surpassed the combined share of agriculture and industry, making it the most important contributor to the country's output. In fiscal year (FY) 2009, services accounted for 57.3 percent of India's GDP¹⁰, which was less than that of countries such as the United Kingdom (UK) at 78.4 percent and the United States (US) at 78.2 percent, but higher than that of the People's Republic of China (PRC) at 41.8 percent¹¹.

The growth of the service sector accelerated in the late 1980s, and by the late 1990s, it had surpassed the growth of industries to become the fastest growing sector of the Indian economy. In FY2009, the service sector grew by 9.96 percent, while the industry sector grew by 8.8% and agriculture grew by 1.57%. 4 From 2001 to 2010, the Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) for services in the PRC and India were 11.3% and 9.4%, respectively¹². This means that, while the PRC's current share of GDP is lower than India's, it will be higher in the future and may even surpass India's because it is growing at a faster rate.

Covid Impact : The COVID-19 Pandemic resulted in global lockdown, and businesses were forced to conduct their operations while keeping Social Distancing in Mind in order to reach out to customers. The sudden or drastic change in business approach caused by the pandemic has caused many players in the service industry to stop their business activities or have seen a drastic decline in their business until they are accustomed to the new way of doing business. Sectors such as education, health care, gym, and tourism have seen a direct impact as the involvement of the people/customers/consumers was limited or completely shut to provide the services. With the government's restrictions on the E-Commerce platform was allowed to operate with a lot of restrictions to provide only essential goods to the borrowers and the service providers came in with

⁹ Asian Development Bank : ADB Economics Working Paper Series (Page 9)

¹⁰ Author's calculations from National Income Accounts. Please note that all calculations are made on GDP at real prices, constant at 1999–2000 and 2004–2005

¹¹ Economic Survey of India 2011–2012.

¹² Economic Survey of India 2011–2012.

the improvement in their services to provide contact less deliveries to the customers at their house¹³.

A few companies from various sectors have seen tremendous growth in their operations as a result of adapting to the changes brought about by the pandemic. As far as the negative impact it has had or the positive impact it has had in evolving the business modules to cater to the needs of customers, it is the only solution to be adjusted and adapted to the challenging situation and help people serve and grow the business.

According to the latest World Investment Report 2020 by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, India moved up from 12th to 9th in the list of the world's largest FDI recipients in 2019. (UNCTAD). FDI into India increased by nearly 17% between April and September 2020 compared to the same period last year, despite the global slowdown, the COVID-19 pandemic, lockdown measures, and supply chain disruptions. During April-September 2020, gross FDI equity inflows (excluding re-invested earnings) into the services sector increased 34% year on year to reach US\$ 23.61 billion, accounting for nearly four-fifths of total gross FDI equity inflows into India during this period. The increase in FDI equity inflows was driven by strong inflows into the 'Computer Software & Hardware' sub-sector, where FDI inflows increased to US\$ 17.55 billion, a 336 percent increase over the same period last year.

Government Initiative: The Government of India recognizes the importance of encouraging growth in the services sector and offers a variety of incentives in areas such as health care, tourism, education, engineering, communications, transportation, information technology, banking, finance, and management, among others. The Government of India has adopted few initiatives in the recent past, some of these are as follows:

- The government allocated Rs. 7,000 crore (US\$ 963.97 million) to the BharatNet programme in the Union Budget 2021-22 to improve digital connectivity across India.
- FDI limit for insurance companies has been raised from 49% to 74% and 100% for insurance intermediates¹⁴.

¹³ India Services Sector A Multi-trillion Dollar Opportunity for Global Symbiotic Growth, A Deloitte-CII report, April 2017

¹⁴ Based on FDI data from Ministry of Commerce

- The third phase of the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) was launched on January 15, 2021, in 600 districts, with 300+ skill courses. The third phase, spearheaded by the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, will concentrate on new-age and COVID-related skills. PMKVY 3.0 aims to train eight lakh candidates.
- The Department of Telecom, Government of India, signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Ministry of Communications, Government of Japan, in January 2021, to strengthen cooperation in the areas of 5G technologies, telecom security, and submarine optical fibre cable system.
- On November 4, 2020, the Union Cabinet, chaired by Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi, approved the signing of a memorandum of understanding (MoU) between the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology and the United Kingdom Government's Department of Digital, Culture, Media, and Sports (DCMS) to collaborate in the field of telecommunications/information and sports technologies of communication (ICTs).
- Hughes Communications India was selected by the government in October 2020 to connect 5,000 village panchayats in border and naxal-affected states and island territories to satellite broadband by March 2021 as part of the BharatNet project.
- The government announced in September 2020 that it may inject Rs. 200 billion (US\$ 2.72 billion) into public sector banks through bond recapitalization. The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology is working to increase the digital economy's contribution to GDP to 20% over the next five years. The government is working to build cloud-based infrastructure for collaborative networks that can be used to create innovative solutions by AI entrepreneurs and startups¹⁵.

Primary Sector

The agriculture sector employs nearly half of the country's workforce. However, it accounts for 17.5% of GDP. Manufacturing and services sectors have increasingly contributed to economic growth over the last few decades, while agriculture's contribution has decreased from more than 50% of GDP in the 1950s to 15.4% in 2015-16. (at constant prices). India's food grain production

¹⁵ Make in India: Which exports can drive the next wave of growth, IMF workingpaper

has increased year after year, and the country ranks among the top producers of several crops, including wheat, rice, pulses, sugarcane, and cotton. It is the world's largest producer of milk and the second largest producer of fruits and vegetables. In 2013, India contributed 25% of the world's pulses production, the highest contribution of any single country, 22% of rice production, and 13% of wheat production. It also accounted for approximately 25% of total cotton production, in addition to being the second largest cotton exporter in recent years.

Agricultural productivity is affected by a variety of factors. These include, among other things, the availability and quality of agricultural inputs such as land, water, seeds, and fertilisers, access to agricultural credit and crop insurance, assurance of remunerative prices for agricultural produce, and storage and marketing infrastructure. This report provides an overview of the state of agriculture in India. It discusses agricultural production and post-harvest activities.

Underemployment and disguised employment are two major issues in this sector. Underemployment accounts for workers who do not work to the best of their abilities, whereas overemployment accounts for workers who do not work to their full potential. As a solution to the problems, the state and national governments can increase funds for irrigation facilities and provide loans for the purchase of high-quality seeds and fertilizers.

Covid- 19 Impact: Uncertainty caused by the crisis, restrictions on inter-state movement, and a lack of transportation disrupted food supply chains, causing food prices to spike and farm operations to suffer. Tomato prices increased by 77–78% in a week and 114–117% in a month following the lockdown. Markets saw increased arrivals in May as a result of distressed sales, and market reforms protected farmers from lower prices. Smaller cities and rural areas saw higher price increases than urban areas. According to survey results, three-quarters of consumers reported a price increase in food commodities during the lockdown. The fear is that the skyrocketing prices will cause social unrest; however, the Indian government has handled the situation deftly with timely market reforms and social safety nets for the poor, migrants, and farmers. Given the scope of the COVID-19 outbreak and the ensuing panic, food prices remained relatively stable. The COVID-19-induced lockdown in India disrupted food markets, forcing consumers to change their consumption patterns. Consumers prioritised what they wanted and what they truly needed. According to various surveys, people lost their jobs or saw their income decrease during the

lockdown. The lockdown, combined with a sudden drop in income, raised serious concerns about food and nutrition security in India.

Perspective Policies to uplift:

- **Social Safety Nets:** The impending shutdown halted production, resulting in job and income losses, as well as a drop in demand. The pandemic also resulted in food loss and waste, which had an impact on the food and beverage industries. Nutritional security, particularly in the vulnerable sector though briefly, and can have long-term effects on capabilities.
- **Price and Revenue Risk Management:** COVID-19 had little or no impact on food prices (except for vegetables). Food prices, on the other hand, are characterised by high volatility, which translates into price risk for farmers.
- **Shifting Focus from Primary to Secondary Agriculture:** COVID-19 induced lockdown has disrupted agricultural labour markets, which have seen massive reverse migration. According to a survey, 45 percent of migrants returned home during the lockdown.
- **Family Farming:** We must keep the concept of sustainability in mind as we plan to strengthen the agricultural sector. Nothing compares to family farming as a model of sustainable food production.
- **Buffer Stock:** Monetizing the excess stock in the buffer could be a source of revenue for the union government. The Food Corporation of India has more than double the buffer stock requirements and is worth at least Rs. 1,50,000 crore.
- **Staggered Procurement and Pricing:** During pandemic situations that disrupt logistics, markets, storage, and so on, the government can opt for a staggered procurement and pricing strategy that accounts for the threshold level in storage cost, particularly for staples like rice and wheat that are produced and consumed by millions.
- **Collective Farming:** Crop farmers should learn from successful examples such as dairy cooperatives in order to increase productivity and profits. Milk prices, unlike cereals, pulses, and vegetables, did not fall the lockdown has an impact
- **Reform in Agriculture finance:** To revitalise the sector, access to low-cost loans, particularly for small and marginal landowners, must be made available. Restructuring

agricultural loans and repayment schedules, as well as deferring the designation of long-term loans as nonperforming assets.

- **Investment in agricultural research and development** : Agriculture and allied sectors grew at a 2.9 percent annual rate between 2014–15 and 2018–19. While the Indian economy contracted by 23.9 percent in the first quarter of 2020–21, agriculture was the only sector to grow by 3.4 percent. It is time to recognise that the agriculture sector may keep the growth engine sputtering if other sectors fail to rise to the occasion, despite farmers facing enormous production and marketing risks even during normal times.
- **Stakeholder's Partnership**: As envisioned in Sustainable Development Goal 17, concerted efforts and inter-institutional collaboration are required to strengthen the weaker and vulnerable segments of society. Stakeholder collaborations help to bridge information and knowledge gaps by raising awareness and leveraging Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) such as social media platforms.

Why did the Lower sector of the economy suffer the most in the Pandemic?

India has always experienced an economic gap between the upper and the lower segments of the economy . Where most of wealth and leverages are enjoyed thoroughly by the upper class and the lower segment suffers all losses. Similar happened during covid 19, where although even the upper segment of the economy suffered few losses, their were much less in compared to the catastrophic effect over the lower segment. The small businesses, agriculture, small industries etc. had to face huge losses both monetarily and personally. Even during this pandemic, the leverage was being provided to the upper segment and the lower segments was left to die. Although Article 14 of the Indian Constitution speaks about equality before law and equal protection before law, but even this could not protect their lives and could not provide them with equal protection from the pandemic. Lack of precautions and lack of infrastructure led to sufferage of the lower segment of the economy even in the second wave of the pandemic.

Sectors of Economy which will Benefit post Covid

The world witnessed one of its worst pandemics ever, and without a doubt, Covid-19 has unimaginably changed the world. India, one of the world's fastest-growing economies, was severely impacted by the pandemic, and the economy experienced a gradual decline during the first wave of the pandemic. The second wave of Covid-19 may not have as severe an impact on the Indian economy as the first wave in 2020, but it is gradually affecting many of the country's most important financial sectors. But, in the midst of all the upheaval and doom, there is a ray of hope. There are many reasons to be cheerful and optimistic. When the pandemic fades and eventually leaves us alone, the post-Covid-19 scenario of the Indian economy leaves us with some potential benefits and will pave the way for upcoming sectors that have the potential to grow in the coming years.

- **E- Retail Sector:** Despite the fact that the majority of Indian households still shop for groceries at neighbourhood stores or visit markets. However, due to the pandemic situation, people have discovered online shopping platforms for groceries such as Big Basket, Nature's Basket, Grofers...etc, which is nothing short of a boon for the E retail Sector, as they have been struggling to draw larger crowds to online platforms for many years. Today's market participants are fully capitalising on the pandemic as an integral part of the everyday grocery fulfilment value chain. At the moment, huge discounts and numerous coupons are being offered on a wide range of products, while unit limits on the purchase of essential goods have been imposed to ensure that everyone's needs are met.
- **Healthcare Sector:** Despite the fact that the healthcare sector has always been an integral part of the country. The pandemic proved to be so destructive that products such as masks, sanitizers, and personal hygiene equipment are expected to increase in popularity, as people adopt better personal hygiene practices in the post-COVID-19 world. Disinfectants and sanitizers are now the most popular products, a trend that is likely to continue and become deeply embedded in consumer behavior. Fitness accessories, such as fitness monitoring devices and applications, are also in high demand. This shift in attitude toward healthy living opens up opportunities for collaboration between fitness product manufacturers and healthcare providers, which will boost the country's GDP in the coming years.
- **Digital Sector:** Prior to the pandemic, the older generation had fewer or fewer options for using digital media. However, things have rapidly changed in the last year as people began to use digital media for work commitments, schooling, and entertainment during the

pandemic. The use of online forums for business meetings has skyrocketed in popularity. Meeting and video calling apps have developed revolutionary features that enable professionals to work from home. This has also made it easier for schools and colleges to begin offering online courses and tests. The lockdown has limited activities that draw a large crowd, such as music festivals, sports, and movies, causing these industries to suffer.

- **Pharmaceuticals:** Since the start of the Covid-19 pandemic, the pharmaceutical industry has been on the rise, particularly in India, the world's largest producer of generic drugs. It has been surging in India, exporting Hydroxychloroquine to the world, particularly to the United States, United Kingdom, Canada, and the Middle East, with a market size of \$55 billion at the beginning of 2020. Because of the pandemic, the prices of raw materials imported from China have recently risen. Because of the industry's reliance on imports, disrupted supply chains, and labour unavailability caused by social distancing, generic drugs are the most impacted.
- **Telecom Sector:** Due to brief price wars between service providers, there has been a significant amount of change in India's telecom sector even before the Covid-19. Because of the implementation of the 'work from home' policy due to restrictions, most essential services and sectors remained operational during the pandemic. As of 2019, the telecom sector employed nearly 4 million people and contributed approximately 6.5 percent of GDP. The increased use of broadband had a direct impact, putting strain on the network. Demand has risen by approximately 10%. Telcos, on the other hand, are bracing for a significant drop in new subscriber additions.

How Banking Sector Helped to revive from Covid crisis?

Between March and June 2020, the World Bank approved \$2.75 billion in emergency lending to support India's response to the COVID-19 crisis, with \$2.25 billion disbursed by December 2020. Of the \$1 billion committed for health support, \$562 million (56 percent) has already been disbursed. The government has continued to commit resources against the remaining amount for the ongoing COVID response. This amount will be disbursed as soon as the supporting documentation from the implementing agencies is received. On December 15, 2020, the Bank committed an additional \$400 million through a second COVID-19-related social protection project, and the funds were disbursed to the government earlier this year.

The initial \$ 2.75 billion lending support covered:

- **Supporting Healthcare Sector:** A \$1 billion COVID-19 Emergency Response and Health System Preparedness Project will assist the country's immediate health needs. More than half of this amount has been disbursed to help strengthen state health facilities, purchase essential medical supplies such as testing equipment and kits, PPEs, gloves, masks, and oxygen cylinders, and insure 2.2 million frontline health workers.
- **Helping Protect People:** Social protection is critical because nearly half of India's households are vulnerable and the majority of the workforce is made up of informal workers. Through the \$1.15 billion Accelerating India's COVID-19 Social Protection Response Program, the World Bank is supporting and strengthening India's social protection programs in order to assist the poor and vulnerable households most affected by the pandemic. The World Bank's assistance is assisting India in developing a social protection system that can meet a wide range of needs by providing portable benefits such as food, social insurance, and cash assistance across state lines. By August 2020, 84 percent of India's poorest households would have received at least one food or cash benefit from the program.
- **Economic Stabilization:** Economic stabilisation, including assistance to approximately 1.5 million small businesses, which are the backbone of the Indian economy, through the \$750 million Emergency Response Program for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. This program is assisting in providing liquidity for MSME balance sheets, mitigating potential solvency issues and job losses, and laying the groundwork for a stronger MSME financing ecosystem once recovery begins. So far, the project has aided in meeting the liquidity and credit needs of over 4 million viable MSMEs.

Conclusion

The impact of pandemic have brought about a number of major changes in all segments of the economy and there has been a paradigm shift towards smartness than conventional methods. But very few have been able to adapt to the changes. Especially the agriculture sector has seen severe losses due to the pandemic and sudden changes in the life style. It is the duty of the law makers to ensure ease in that change and duty of the administration to implement it smoothly. "Change is

inevitable” as they say, therefore to move about with the change we need to have a strong backbone i.e strong economy. This pandemic showed us that even our Fundamental rights are not permanent in nature, they can be taken away in case of ay emergency, but the fact is that Right to life is away from any change. Therefore to comply with Article 21, all sectors has to be aided equivalently so that they have reasonable amont of support for survival through any harsh condition.

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